

**THE INFLUENCE OF BILLBOARD ADVERTISING ON ELECTORATE'S VOTING
DECISION: A STUDY OF THE 2019 CROSS RIVER STATE GUBERNATORIAL
CAMPAIGN**

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of billboard advertising on electorate's voting decision during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial campaign. The study sought to ascertain the level of relevance attached to billboards as a means of political information by the electorates, to find out if the electorate in Cross River State actually believed in the political messages presented on the billboards, as well as to ascertain if the electorate were actually influenced by the billboard messages. To achieve these, relevant concepts and empirical studies were reviewed and the agenda setting theory as well as the social marketing theory were adopted in the study to establish a workable theoretical framework. The study employed the mixed method with the questionnaire and interview inventory as research instrument. Through multi-stage sampling, 399 respondents were selected for survey from the three senatorial districts in Cross River state and 2 interviewees for in-depth interview. The findings indicated among other things, that electorates in Cross River State were significantly influenced by their exposure to these billboards and most of them were persuaded not only by the messages but by the visual composition of the billboard. The study found out that the billboards are at a better advantage over the handheld printed communication media, these which might be easily misplaced by an individual. In the light of the findings, the study concluded that the billboard can be used both for political campaigning and for political orientation/education. With these, it was recommended that billboards should be constructed with materials that will be able to withstand any weather condition without being damaged in order to sustain its messages. Its messages can as well be written in local dialects in order to induce the desired results from the electorate. The study also recommended that the government should adopt billboards as major tools for political education and electoral orientation.

Keywords: *Electorate, Election, Voter, Gubernatorial, Billboard, Media, Political Campaign*

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Out-of-home (OOH) Advertising is the second-fastest-growing media category, after the Internet. Billboards and posters viewed while moving are included. It also includes location-based media, which can be found in convenience stores, medical centres, and other physical locations.

A billboard (also known as a hoarding) is a huge outdoor advertising structure (a billing board) that is often seen in high-traffic locations such as expressways and highways. Passing pedestrians and automobiles see enormous advertisements on billboards. Billboards are highly visible in the top designated market locations, usually with funny phrases and striking images. According to Bartle (2014), the largest ordinary-sized billboards are typically found on major roads, expressways, or major arterials, where they receive high-density consumer exposure (mostly to vehicular traffic). These provide the most notice, not just because of their size, but also because they allow for creative "customizing" with extensions and embellishments.

Billboard advertisements are intended to rapidly capture a person's attention and leave a lasting impression, leaving the reader wondering about the advertisement long after they have passed it. Because they are generally viewed at high speeds, they must be readable in a very short amount of time. As a result, there are usually only a few phrases in huge size and a brightly colored graphic that is amusing or arresting. Parts of the figures hang off the billboard edges or jut out in three dimensions, while other designs spill aesthetically outside the real space provided to them on the billboard (Siang, 2020).

Billboard advertising is useful for raising awareness and communicating goals to a large number of people. When compared to other advertising tactics, billboards get the maximum number of views and impressions because they are located in such busy regions (Decker, 2019).

According to Wroblewski (2018), "digital billboards have improved this advertising strategy, particularly in the twenty-first century." Whether or not you agree with this argument, there is no denying that billboards have some distinct advantages as a business and political communication tool.

Political communication, on the other hand, refers to organized political campaigning aimed at influencing the decision-making process inside a given group. Political campaigns in democracies frequently relate to electoral campaigns in which political leaders are elected or referendums are resolved. The most high-profile political campaigns in modern politics are centered on general elections and candidates.

The candidate's campaign messages contain the ideas that he or she wishes to convey to voters. When running for a political office, it is to enlist the support of individuals who share their beliefs. Several talking points about policy concerns are frequently included in the message. The bullet points highlight the campaign's essential arguments and are repeated frequently to leave a lasting impact on voters. For any democratic system to exist, political parties and politicians must give voters with sufficient information about party policies, a clear vision, and their political objectives, allowing voters to make informed decisions about their candidates (Holtved, 2011).

During campaigns, political parties employ billboards to do this. In any community, billboards serve an important role in keeping citizens informed about current events and creating awareness about various topics (being a medium of communication). It also has a significant influence on public opinion and thinking. Billboards are one of the tools used to shape and sometimes control public opinion. Simply expressed, the electorate must have sufficient information of the candidates, political parties, and election policies for an election to be called free and fair.

Election campaign techniques in the past emphasized personal interaction and political rallies. However, since Nigeria's shift from military to democratic administration, political ad campaigns have grown in popularity, owing to a growing understanding of the media's power (Oche, 2010). As a result, political parties and politicians all over the world invest heavily in political advertising campaigns in order to position themselves as the preferred brand among voters. Citizens are more likely to believe a candidate who creates his or her campaign statements to reflect the battle to improve voters' lives, and if the words have a high level of integrity.

In other words, voters are more likely to trust candidates whose political billboard ads promise to provide their basic needs and wants rather than candidates who focus solely on their personal accomplishments. In political billboard ads, however, personality, look, and language play important roles. Meanwhile, the effectiveness of political billboards in influencing voters to vote for a candidate is still debatable (Ojekwe, 2016).

Political parties and candidates in Cross River State were heavily involved in political campaigns for the 2019 gubernatorial elections, displaying various campaign information on billboards of various sizes in an attempt to obtain votes from citizens. In the end, the People's Democratic Party's (PDP) nominee Benedict Ayade was re-elected as governor of Cross River State. His political campaigns, which included billboards with his photos and strategic comments, had taken over the streets, local government regions, and towns for every class of voter. His jingles, which were broadcast on radio and television stations as well as social media sites, were complemented by the billboard campaign.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The transient/ephemeral aspect of billboard advertising, which has a negative impact on communication, is a major problem as identified in this research study. Anyone driving down the motorways is bound to run across multiple political campaign billboards, yet it is unclear how those information are received. Billboards only target mobile audiences, and it is impossible to know what kind of impression they will have on them. Its use may become ineffective if the intended audience (electorate) are not always on the road.

Furthermore, political billboards do not only include colorful designs, but also contain convincing messages that detail what the candidates would do for the people if elected. Billboards have the ability to capture the attention of the target population as a means of political communication, however it is unclear if the voters will respond to or align with these statements.

Hence, the influence of billboards on the electorate voting decision during the 2019 gubernatorial campaigns in Cross River State, Nigeria, is investigated.

1.3 Research Questions

R₁

What level of relevance did the electorate in Cross River State attach to billboards as means of political communication during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial campaign?

R₂

Did the electorates in Cross River State believe in the political messages presented on the billboards during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial campaign?

R₃

How did the political billboards messages influence/affect the electorates' decision of voting during the 2019 gubernatorial campaign?

1.4 Significance of Study

The findings of this study will be of paramount importance to the following:

1. **Political Parties:** The results of this study will recommend the appropriate standard and model of billboard campaign necessary to be crafted and displayed by the political parties towards improvements in the forthcoming 2023 elections
2. **Graphic Designers:** This study will recommend the designing elements necessary for adoption on campaign billboards.
3. **Electorate:** The study will help the electorates understand better the importance of billboard advertising during electioneering campaigns.
4. **Political Science Students:** the contents of this study which is centered on the development of political communication in this regard shall be of interest to students in the political science discipline.
5. **Mass Communication students:** This study shall emphasize significantly on the concepts of advertising and print communication and this will be of interest to the students of mass communication discipline.
6. **CRUTECH:** this study shall be of interest to the Cross River University of Technology, to serve as her contribution towards societal development.

1.5 Scope of Study

This study covers Cross River State of Nigeria which is comprised of eighteen (18) Local Government Areas and focuses on Calabar Municipality, Ikom and Ogoja LGAs selected from the

three senatorial districts within the State. It will significantly assess the influence of billboards on the outcomes of the Cross River 2019 gubernatorial elections which were compiled and presented in Calabar (the state's capital).

The study will cover from the pre-electoral period (when the aspirants began their billboard campaigns) to the electoral period - when the electorate (having been exposed to the billboards messages) were made to cast their votes.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Advertising

Advertising is a form of commercial communication in which a product, service, or concept is promoted or sold through an explicitly sponsored, non-personal message (Shiproh, 2007). Businesses that want to market their products or services are often advertising sponsors. Advertising differs from public relations in that the advertiser pays for the message and has control over it. It varies from personal selling in that the message is not personalized, that is, it is not directed at a specific person.

Advertising is at the forefront of getting the right message out to customers and prospects. The goal of advertising is to inform customers about a company's product and persuade them that their services or products are the best, to improve the company's image, to identify and create a need for products or services, to demonstrate new uses for existing products, to announce new products and programs, to reinforce salespeople's individual messages, to attract new customers, and to retain existing customers (Shiproh, 2007).

In various parts of the world, billboards are big advertising structures erected in public locations that display advertisements to passing pedestrians and automobiles. They are most commonly found on major roads with a lot of passing automotive and pedestrian traffic; but, they can be found in any site with a lot of people, such as on mass transit vehicles and stations, retail malls or office buildings, and stadiums. Using huge moveable structures (tents) in public spaces on a temporary basis, sheltered outdoor advertising mixes outdoor and inside advertising. The product is advertised indoors, where the innovative decor can strengthen the impression, while the big exterior advertising area tries to impose a powerful pull on the viewer. Mobile billboards or digital screens are usually put on vehicles. These can be on specialist vehicles created specifically for transporting advertisements along routes chosen by clients, highly outfitted cargo trucks, or even giant banners dispersed from planes.

Billboards are frequently illuminated, with some being backlit and others using spotlights. Some billboard displays are static, while others fluctuate, such as rotating advertisements continually or sporadically. Target advertising, one-day and long-term campaigns, conventions, athletic events, store openings and similar promotional events, and large billboards from smaller enterprises are all examples of how mobile displays are employed in urban regions around the world.

2.1.2 Impacts/Effectiveness of billboard advertising

Billboards that are effective must have a clear, succinct message, appealing images, and a pleasing aesthetic look (Achien'g, 2009). They should be as clutter-free and easy to read as possible. Because they only have 2-4 seconds of an individual's attention, the message must be simple to comprehend. It is difficult to evaluate the value and efficacy of billboard advertising. Newspaper ads and direct mail campaigns are two examples of advertising that yield outcomes that are easier to evaluate. The difference with billboard advertising is that it reaches a large audience, but there is no way to determine who truly understands the message. Methodologies have been used to assess efficacy, although their validity has been questioned.

Billboard advertising has a particularly strong psychological influence, given to the channel's unique nature and how voters interact with it. While this may appear weird, it can be explained by the unconscious mind's amazing processing capacity, which can analyze up to 11 million pieces of data every second. The conscious mind, on the other hand, can only process 40 pieces of data in the same amount of time, limiting its ability to handle enormous amounts of data in real time (Inman, 2018).

In this way, the subconscious mind functions like a sponge, absorbing information from its surrounds and the surrounding natural environment. Given the ability of billboards to blend in organically and seamlessly with their surroundings, it is apparent that voters are receptive to campaign messaging provided through this medium, whether they are aware of it or not. This also undermines the conscious mind's predisposition to judge information based on its nature and the source from which it was obtained.

Billboards increase conversion rates by creating familiarity; as humans, we are averse to change, even when it has the potential to be beneficial (Hayward-Cole, 2019). This is because some humans

are more likely to do things that make them feel pleased, secure, and fundamentally comfortable than to try new things that are outside of their comfort zones. This mindset has a significant impact on the attitudes of voters, who prioritize election candidates they are already familiar with, and they tend to seek out political parties they know and trust to help them solve their problem (Wolf, 2017); this is where outdoor advertising comes into play, as larger-than-life billboards placed in strategic locations helped to build candidates' awareness and drive recognition over a long period of exposure.

2.1.3 Concept of Gubernatorial Election

One of the key features of an emergent democratic system is the institutions that are established and constitute the respective parts of the entire system. Elections and institutions that carry out electoral processes are not only central to the entire democratic system, but also attract significant attention because they facilitate the process of legitimizing leadership (Oche, 2010). This they do through voting processes and through also facilitating the systematic acquisition and transfer of political power.

Gubernatorial election is a primary key feature of a democratic system and it can be traced back to the 1700s when it first began in the United States. Gubernatorial simply refers to the governor (Swifter, 2017) and the voting process that brings a governor into power and as well vesting gubernatorial powers on the governor is known to be the gubernatorial election.

Every four years, Nigeria conducts elections for these elected political offices in three phases: National Assembly elections, presidential elections, and gubernatorial as well as state Assembly elections. The 2019 election season in Nigeria, which kicked off on February 23 with the National Assembly polls, followed by Presidential elections on the same date preceded the last phase of the election season which included the gubernatorial and state assembly election that took place on March 9.

The 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election was conducted on March 9 to choose the Governor of Cross River State. The election was held concurrently with various state level elections. Governor Benedict Ayade on September 30, 2018 emerged the governorship candidate of PDP for the 2019 elections through affirmation by delegates at the party's primary election. He

won the APC flag bearer John Owan-Enoh at a direct general election in March 2019 and hence eligible to run for second term under PDP. He polled 381,484 votes to defeat the APC that polled 131,161 (Ikechukwu, 2019).

2.2 Empirical Review/Gaps

In a study titled "Political Adverts Campaigns and Voting Behaviour: Akinwumi Ambode's 2015 Election Campaign in Lagos State," Ojekwe (2016) examined the efficacy of political ads campaigns used in Nigerian elections, in order to determine the extent to which Akinwumi Ambode's ads campaign influenced voters' choices in Lagos state and the most effective campaign strategy used by the gubernatorial candidate. The research scope and methodology are two of the gaps covered in the current study. While this recent study focused only on Akinwumi Ambode's ad campaign during the 2015 Lagos state gubernatorial election, the present study looks at billboard advertisements from all competing political parties during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election. The recent study employs only the survey method in the collation of data for analyses unlike the current study which collates data through the survey and in-depth interview (mixed) methodologies for deeper insights.

Tejumaiye et al. (2018) published a paper titled "Political Advertising in Nigeria's 2015 Presidential Election" in this regard. The goal of the study was to see if political advertising alone had an impact on voters' voting decisions in the 2015 presidential election. Meanwhile, the current study addresses this recent study's proximity and specification shortcomings. Unlike the previous study, which was done three years after the election year (2015), the current study is conducted two years after the election year (2019), giving it a higher proximate quality. Also, the previous study was not specific in the type(s) of advertising media used in analyzing the influence of political advertising on electorates' decision but the current study is specific - emphasizing more on the billboard medium.

Ngwoke (2016) conducted research on "Public Perceptions of Billboard Advertising During the 2015 General Election Campaign Period: A Case Study of Enugu North Metropolis." The purpose of the study was to determine the amount of importance attributed to billboards as a source of political information during election seasons and to see if billboard messages influenced voters in

Enugu North Metropolis during the 2015 general election campaigns. Unlike the current study, which evaluates, includes, and groups the entire Local Government Areas in Cross River State into three senatorial districts for broader research coverage, the study area was limited to the Enugu North Metropolis exclusively.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The agenda-setting and social marketing theories are used to validate the study's concepts and topics in order to assess the scope and influence of billboards as a communication channel. According to McCombs and Shaw (1968), agenda framing is accomplished through a cognitive process known as "accessibility." In the context of this study, "accessibility" means that the more popular and prominently billboard advertisements cover a candidate, a political party, or election related material, the more times that element of coverage becomes accessible in the audience's recollections. During the 2019 gubernatorial campaign, the contesting political parties launched over 2000 posters and complementary billboards in every corner of the state (Nyok, 2021), not only to reach out to the electorates, but also to access their minds with the billboards' contents, thus influencing their perceptions, impacting on their choice, and educating them on the biometric pattern of voting. The agenda-setting effect is caused by the cumulative impact of a large number of communications, each of which has a different substance but all of which deal with the same general subject.

On the other hand, Social marketing aims to comprehend the social and psychological aspects that contribute to societal reluctance to change (Levit and Cismaru, 2020). It improves the target group's acceptance, responsiveness, and practise of any social idea. Market segmentation, exchange theory, and consumer research are all common marketing techniques. Operational social marketing and strategic social marketing are the two types of social marketing (Narwhal, 2021). Operational social marketing is used to influence behaviour, while strategic social marketing is used to generate new policies and development initiatives. The theory is significant to this study because it gives a framework for planning, creating, implementing, and evaluating social campaigns with the primary goal of information sharing.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The mixed method was employed in this study as it appeared to be the most suitable for gathering data for this study. This study incorporates the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies in gathering of data, which enhances the level of comprehension of the study. Qualitative research is expressed in words. This method of research enables one to gather in-depth insights on topics that are not well understood. Survey research method, through the questionnaire, was adopted for the quantitative research. This is because of the large population as the instrument can be sent across the entire population thus enabling the population in the selected Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Cross River State to participate in the process conveniently.

3.2 Areas of Study

For the purpose of this study, three (3) Local Government Areas from the three senatorial districts in Cross River State were considered, these which included; Calabar Municipality (Southern senatorial district), Ikom (Central senatorial district) and Ogoja (Northern senatorial district).

3.3 Population of Study

The population of the study were the total number of registered voters in the three sampled LGAs which are 361,569 persons (Okay, n.d.).

3.4 Sample size and Sample Technique

The sample size for the questionnaire was obtained using the Taro-Yamane (1967) formula to extract a minimum sample size. The formula states thus;

The formula states thus;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = Population under study

e = the margin error and is usually 0.10, 0.05 or 0.01

1 = Constant

thus;

$$N = 361\ 569$$

$$e = 0.005$$

$$n = \frac{361\ 569}{1+361\ 569(0.005)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{361\ 569}{1+ 361\ 569 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{361\ 569}{1 + 903.9225}$$

$$n = \frac{361\ 569}{904.9225}$$

$$n = 399$$

Therefore, a sample size of three hundred and ninety-nine (399) respondents was drawn for this study across the three local government areas in focus.

Table 3.1 Proportionate Distribution of the Population

LGA	Registered Voters per LGA	Percentage (%) of Population	Sample size
Calabar Municipality	166066	45.93%	183
Ikom	105769	29.25%	116
Ogoja	89734	24.82%	100
TOTAL	361 569	100%	399

Using the multistage procedure, the study area (Cross River State) was divided into three senatorial districts using the cluster sampling technique. One local government area each in the clusters were randomly selected, thus, Ogoja LGA, Ikom LGA and Calabar Municipality LGA. From each of these Local Government Areas, one town each were randomly selected and they included: Abakpa, Yala-Nkum and Calabar. These towns were divided into streets (units) and twelve (12) streets in each town were randomly selected. In all, 36 streets were randomly selected for the purpose of this study. To select individual respondents from each of the 12 streets, the study adopted the convenient sampling technique. As such, samples who were present at the time of administering the questionnaire were given a copy of the questionnaire to complete. The purposive sampling technique was employed in selecting key interviewees for the in-depth interview approach.

3.5 Data Collection and Analysis

The study employed the questionnaire and interview guide as instruments for data collection. Data obtained from the survey were presented and analyzed using the Frequency/Percentage Distribution table, the bar chart and the pie chart methods of data analysis. Data from the in-depth interview were transcribed verbatim.

3.6. Ethical Consideration

Before starting a research project, it is vital to have a well-defined issue and study question in mind, since there are ethical considerations to keep in mind (Nardi, 2021). The relationship between the researcher and the participants in the study is an important aspect. An important concern is if the study may purposefully hurt or infringe on the private rights of persons participating in the study, whether emotionally or physically (Nardi, 2021). If participants are not given the opportunity to provide their informed permission, data may be utilized in ways they were not intended for (Baran and Davies, 2006). Due to the risk of informed consent being compromised, such deception should be avoided in study.

Data analysis and research findings presentation must incorporate ethical considerations into account as well (Nardi, 2021). A biased result can only be produced if data and statistical computations used to get at it are presented and understood correctly, which means the findings should not be dishonest or prejudiced in favor of the good outcome. The above-mentioned ethical standards were taken into account as far as feasible in this investigation. All stages of the study were taken into account, but the self-completion questionnaire, which was the primary means of communication between researchers and participants, was given particular attention. The purpose of the research has been made explicit in the research instrument (questionnaire cover letter) (see Appendix A), as well as the fact that participation was optional and that the individuals' replies could not be linked back to them.

Various statistical metrics would also be used in the analysis after data gathering and would not be manipulated in any manner, to influence the interpretation of the data.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION/ANALYSES

4.1 Introduction

Out of the administered three hundred and ninety-nine (399) copies of questionnaire to the residents in Abakpa, Yala Nkum and Calabar towns, three hundred and ninety-one (391) copies of the questionnaire were correctly filled and returned. This accounted for 97.9% success rate. Eight (8) copies were not correctly filled or returned, accounting for 2.0% failure rate. Thus, with a success rate of 97.9%, the data collected from the field were deemed representative enough for the population of the study as presented above.

4.2 Demographic Analysis

Respondents' Occupational Distribution

Respondents' Age Distribution

Respondents' Choicest Political Party

4.3 Psychographic Analysis

TABLE 4.1 Reactions to Billboards relevance in political information dissemination.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	150	38.3
Agree (A)	150	38.3
Undecided (U)	20	5.1
Disagree (D)	40	10.2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	31	8
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.2: Reactions to Billboards relevance over other media of political advertising.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	98	25
Agree (A)	100	25.5
Undecided (U)	50	13
Disagree (D)	90	23
Strongly Disagree (SD)	53	13.5
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.3: Reactions to the effects of billboards information on the electorates' attitudes towards the electoral process.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	189	48.3
Agree (A)	98	25
Undecided (U)	10	2.5
Disagree (D)	60	15.3
Strongly Disagree (SD)	34	9
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.4: Reactions to Billboards contributions to the electorates' choice of candidates.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	90	23
Agree (A)	180	46
Undecided (U)	1	0.2
Disagree (D)	70	18
Strongly Disagree (SD)	50	13
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.5: Reactions to Billboards usefulness in electoral orientation.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	102	26
Agree (A)	208	53
Undecided (U)	11	3
Disagree (D)	50	13
Strongly Disagree (SD)	20	5
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.6: Reactions to billboards dense placements around the State.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	120	31
Agree (A)	90	23
Undecided (U)	60	15
Disagree (D)	70	18
Strongly Disagree (SD)	51	13
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.7 Reactions to electorates' belief in the billboard as a medium for political advertising.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	200	51
Agree (A)	120	31
Undecided (U)	16	4
Disagree (D)	44	11
Strongly Disagree (SD)	11	3
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.8: Reactions to the influence of ethnic background on electorates' belief in the billboard messages.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	6	1
Agree (A)	15	4
Undecided (U)	50	13
Disagree (D)	200	51
Strongly Disagree (SD)	120	31
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.9: Reactions to the influence of religious affiliations on electorates' consumption of billboard messages.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	40	10
Agree (A)	160	41
Undecided (U)	10	2
Disagree (D)	100	25
Strongly Disagree (SD)	81	21
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.10: Reactions to the contribution of the advertised political party on the electorates' belief in the genuinity of the messages.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	200	51
Agree (A)	150	38
Undecided (U)	12	3
Disagree (D)	20	5
Strongly Disagree (SD)	9	2
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.11: Reactions to the conviction of billboard pictures on the electorates.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	180	46
Agree (A)	191	49
Undecided (U)	5	1
Disagree (D)	8	2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	7	1
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.12: Reactions to the contribution of billboards' visual elements in the conviction of the electorates.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	200	51
Agree (A)	160	41
Undecided (U)	5	1
Disagree (D)	15	4
Strongly Disagree (SD)	11	3
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.13: Reactions to the influence of the extra-large billboards over the smaller ones.

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	120	31
Agree (A)	40	10
Undecided (U)	205	52
Disagree (D)	25	6
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1	0
TOTAL	391	100

TABLE 4.14: Reactions to the impacts of brief billboards messages over lengthy messages''

Options	Frequency (r)	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree (SA)	180	46
Agree (A)	100	25
Undecided (U)	6	1
Disagree (D)	70	18
Strongly Disagree (SD)	35	9
TOTAL	391	100

4.4 In-depth Interview Summary

Interviewee 1: Mr. Efiok Ita Nyok (*Head of publicity affairs to Mr. Eyo Ekpo – a 2019 CRS gubernatorial candidate, Social Democratic Party*)

Date: 16th July, 2021 **Location:** Conflict management & Peace Mediation Seminar Centre, Calabar

Summarily, the interviewee stated that the Social Democratic Party (SDP) equally adopted the billboard as one of its campaign medium during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election. He added that CRISAA (Cross River State Signage and Advertising Agency) had frustrated their extensive usage of campaign billboards around the state owing to political sentiments and discrimination. In his statement “political parties do not depend on the communication strategy of the billboards alone to win election. It is one thing for the billboard to be located in strategic locations but other things applies which may include vote buying, election rigging and the electoral processes. The billboard message is only there for the masses’ consumption but the decision of the voters and the entire stakeholders involved in the electoral process including INEC is a different ball game. In his word, “Notwithstanding, sometimes when we go to the nooks and crannies of the state, people easily identify with us not because they have met us before but because our physical description matches some of the elements that are already reflected on the billboard.” The interviewee pointed out that the billboards go ahead of them to send the message even before their arrival, creates the desired awareness and even after their departure, the billboards stands as a memorial to sustain the memories of previous encounters.

Interviewee 2: Mr. Effanga Effiong (*Chief Executive Officer, Digital Graphics House, Calabar*)

Date: 20th July, 2021 **Location:** Digital Graphics House, Calabar

Summarily, the interviewee pointed out clearly that the nature of the billboard cannot be taken away from the billboard, putting it that it can never come to a point where billboards will be squeezed into vehicles or mounted inside the house for continuous viewership and if this would ever happen at all, then such technology has gone out of the scope of the billboard and as such,

should be given another identity. He pointed clearly that crafting a message of long sentences with complex diction will not only mar the communication objective but will defeat the initial essence and purpose of communication. The interviewee stated that there are various formats and sizes for billboard design, nevertheless a graphic designer should be able to determine which layout and format will fit in well for an electoral situation.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The findings according to the research questions posed are discussed as follows;

Research Question One: What level of relevance did the electorates in Cross River State attach to billboards as means of political communication during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial campaign?

Billboards are relevant enough to serve the purposes of political communication, candidates marketing, mass persuasion and electoral orientations. Electorates in Cross River State actually believed in the relevance of the billboard during the 2019 gubernatorial election. According to data on table 4.1, 38.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that the billboards were relevant, another 38.3% agreed to its relevance, 5.1% were undecided, 10.2% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed to this.

The findings of this study aligns with Ngwoke (2016) who asserts that all those who voted during the 2015 general elections were aware of political Billboards in Enugu and the rest who still did not vote accepted the fact that they saw the Billboards. As stated in her findings, "it also appeared easy for voters (respondents) to agree that the billboard is a better political medium than other media of political advert" and this further establishes the survey findings on table 4.2 which points out that 25% of the respondents strongly agreed that Billboards are more relevant than the other media of political advertising, 25.5% agreed to this, 13% were undecided, 23% disagreed and 13.5% strongly disagreed to this. This findings strongly argues with Ezegwu et al (2015) who opines that the electorates should not rely on billboard advert or campaign as the only source of information about contestants. It should explore other sources such as radio, television, social

media, friends and party members who could offer useful information for its voting decision, because billboard messages are always brief and cannot tell all about a candidate.

Research Question Two: Did the electorates in Cross River State believe in the political messages presented on the billboards during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial campaign?

Political messages are the strategic and planned contents of a political campaign medium/media which are consciously targeted at the electorates within a particular area or location with the main purpose of influencing their voting choices and decisions. Data from table 4.7 reveal that 51% of the respondents strongly believed in the political messages presented on the Billboards during the 2019 CRS gubernatorial election, 31% believed in the messages, 4% neither believed or not, 11% disbelieved the messages and 3% strongly disbelieved the political messages.

The findings of this study support the social marketing theory which implies the design, implementation, and control of programmes calculated to influence the acceptability of social ideas and involving considerations of publicity message planning, design, communication, distribution, and response survey. This theory tries to show clearly how social and psychological factors work to increase the effectiveness of mass media information campaigns. Narwhal (2021) points out that the social marketing theory possess six (6) distinct features, all of which contributes to the persuasion and conviction of the electorates' belief system. These features include; audience awareness, targeting the right audience, reinforcing the message, cultivating images/impressions, stimulating interest in the target audience and inducing desired results.

Every political messages trends to portray these features and this supports the assertion by Tejumaiye et al (2018) that political advertising tends to reinforce the electorates' choice of candidates. Choice reinforcement as an objective of a political communication plan will guide the crafting process of a strategic message that will thereafter influence the electorates' beliefs and as identified by Nyok, E. (personal communication, July 16th, 2021), billboards plays a pivotal role in reinforcing and impacting the electorates' choices even before their encounters with the political actors in-persons. To this end, this finding argues with Ngwoke (2016) who found out that the

billboards are compellingly attractive but the choice of candidate does not even come into play when the electorates look at or admire the billboards.

Research Question Three: How did the political billboards messages influence/affect the electorates' decision of voting during the 2019 gubernatorial campaign?

The electorates in Cross River State were actually influenced by the messages displayed on the billboards and the reinforcement/conviction of their choice of candidates through these messages was credited to several other visual factors which determined the individual's visual appreciation for aesthetics. Data from tables 4.11, 4.12 and 4.13 shows that the various design elements (which are the basic units of any visual design) formed the billboard's structure and conveyed the political messages visually. According to Siang (2020), such visual elements Includes line, shape, negative/white space, volume, value, colour and texture. These elements should be appropriately composed in relations with the basic principles of visual design as identified by Hayward-Cole (2019) which includes balance, alignment, hierarchy, contrast and rhythm.

The findings of this study demonstrates that a strategic message over a well composed visual background on the billboards will definitely capture the electorates' attention, register the message/design composure in their sub-consciousness, keep them thinking and talking about it whenever it occurs to them and goes on to reinforce/influence their choices. This finding establishes Effanga, E. (personal communication, July 20th, 2021) who stated that the principles and elements of designs must be appropriately applied to avoid misconceptions and to achieve the objective of public persuasion. Nevertheless, this can be understood more in relation to the agenda setting theory which is based on the assumption that when an issue is covered prominently, the audience will regard the issue as more important. This theory describes the way that media attempts to influence public opinions/interactions, and establish a hierarchy of prevalence; it implies the creation of public awareness and concern of salient issues by the media. This therefore challenges Ezegwu et al (2015) who asserts that "the influence of these billboard campaigns are limited to what people allowed it to be."

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

5.1 Summary

The 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election was conducted on the 9th of March, 2019 and prior to this, the state had witnessed an aggressive campaign movements orchestrated by the election candidates who streamed from different registered political parties. The political campaigns had involved the usage of various communication media for the dissemination of strategic messages aimed at influencing the masses. Notable as one of the employed media was the billboards which were strategically positioned in the key areas around the state. In this regard, this research was conducted in view of the influence of billboard advertising on the electorates' voting decision. It was conducted in view of the place of billboards as a mass medium and in the context which media affects research and political communication. From the objectives, research questions were raised to aid the research process. To provide a comprehensive background for the research findings, the researcher had reviewed previous literature that were relevant to the study. Two theories, the agenda setting theory and the social marketing theory were used to establish the study's theoretical framework.

The research design employed in this work was the mixed method and a total of 401 participants (399 respondents and 2 interviewees) were sampled using the multi-stage sampling technique. Data collected from the field survey were analyzed using the pie and bar charts as well as the frequency distribution tables. Thus, the analyzed data presented the following significant findings;

1. Political Billboards are subject to the placement regulations of the outdoor-adverts regulatory agencies.
2. Several factors determines a political party's victory in an election, billboards notwithstanding. Such factors may include, votes buying, election rigging and electoral body's decision.
3. The visual design of the billboard's layout is as important as the political message on it - both plays the role of public persuasion.

4. The billboards are at a better advantage over other printed political communication media (such as flyers, handbills etc - these which might be easily misplaced by an individual).

5. Billboards are not mere political campaign traditions, they serve as veritable platforms for the dissemination of a strategic message which is consciously aimed at influencing the masses.

5.2 Conclusion

The adoption of billboards as a medium of political communication goes beyond political competitions as may be perceived by anyone existing within the political sphere. Billboard is a strategic communication platform and in support of Achien'g (2009), effective billboard communication must be built around concise message, attractive illustrations and visual appearance.

The role of billboards in political communication is not central, rather, it is multifaceted and this owes significantly to the varieties of elements employed in its composition and layout. Therefore, while a voter may be initially attracted to a billboard by reason of its message, another voter may be attracted to it by reason of its visual composition. But, whatever the case may be, Inman (2018) supports that billboard has the ability to attract attention and to register its message on the viewer's sub-consciousness.

During election, the electorate most likely reminiscences on the political messages and images previously encountered on a billboard (through the incredible processing abilities of the mind) and these contributes immensely to the electorate's voting decision

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the statistical analyses of the research questions, the following recommendations are made for the study;

1. Government should adopt billboards as major tools for political education and electoral orientation. Billboards messages should not be relegated only to the function of candidates' publicity during political campaigns; such messages can be employed as a strategy towards mobilizing the masses for political sensitization.
2. Political messages meant to be displayed on the billboards should be concise and straight to the point, void of any fluctuation and ambiguity.
3. Design elements applied in the interpretation of the political billboard's intents should be composed based on and guided by the basic principles of visual communication to avoid misconceptions.
4. Billboards messages can be written in local dialects in order to drive the right message and induce the desired results from the electorate. Illustrations should include what the non-educated segment of the electorate will be able to decode and comprehend easily.
5. Political parties and candidates should make good use of billboards in selling their manifestos (as part of the political message) to the general public during the political campaigns. This will definitely increase the possibility of influencing the electorates' decisions.
6. Billboards placement regulations by the regulatory agencies should not be on the basis of political sentiments and bias. Genuine regulations will facilitate the advertisers' objectives of influencing the general populace.
7. Billboards should be constructed with materials that will be able to withstand any weather condition without being damaged. The ability of the billboards to last for a longer period of time (especially during the political campaigns period) will keep its message ringing.

5.4 Limitations

Every study has limitations. Study limitations can exist due to constraints on research design or methodology, and these factors may impact the findings of the study. However, many researchers are reluctant to discuss the limitations encountered in the course of their study in their papers, feeling that bringing up limitations may undermine its research value in the eyes of readers and reviewers. In spite of these, the limitations so encountered in the course of this study includes;

- Time constraints: the short while allocated for the gathering of data and compilation of results regarding this study was short coupled with involvements in other academic coursework and these affected the study to an extent.
- Uncooperative respondents: interactions with some respondents who were not patient enough to understand the importance of the study nor willing to divulge useful information led to the inability to gather relevant facts and figures as necessary.
- Network connections: this was also a problem associated with the accessing of relevant research materials and other empirical studies. The fluctuations in network coverage was an impediment to a hitch-free research.

Nevertheless, I was able to provide all facts and figures accurately and reasonably with a corresponding and valid bibliography.

REFERENCES

- Achien'g, J. A. (2009) "Effectiveness of billboard advertising: A case of soft drinks in Nairobi. Retrieved from the University of Nairobi, Lower Kabete library (online). Retrieved via <https://www.uonlibrary.uonbi.ac.ke> On March 6th, 2021.
- Baran, S. J., & Davis, D. R. (2006). *Mass Communication Theory Foundations*, Ferment and Future (4th ed.). Belmont Thomson Wadsworth.
- Bartle, Hannah (2014). "Pros and Cons of outdoor Advertising. Retrieved via <https://www.auburnadvertising.com> On March 6th, 2021.
- Decker, A. (2019). "Everything you need to know about billboard advertising" Retrieved via <https://www.blog.hubspot.com> On Monday 8th March, 2021.
- Effiong, E. (2021). Personal communication [Personal interview].
- Ezegwu, D., Ezeji, A., & Agbasimelo, C. J. (2015). "A comparative study of the influence of Goodluck Jonathan and Mohammadu Buhari's billboard campaign on voters behaviours in Anambra State. *Communication Panoram African and global perspective Vol. 1 No. 2, Nov-Dec 2015 issue*. <https://doi.org/65.554/eng.2015.e113>
- Hayward-Cole, V. (2019). "7 basic principles of graphic design". Retrieved via <https://www.lcca.org.uk/blog/careers/7-basic-principles-of-graphic-design> On July 21st, 2021.
- Holtved, Ole (2011). "Biometrics in elections". *Interactive foundation for electoral systems and USAID*. Retrieved via <https://www.jogger.org> On July 21st, 2021.
- Inman, Paul (2019). "Psychological impacts of Billboard Advertising". Retrieved via <https://www.cashch.com> On March 6th, 2021.
- Levit, T. & Cismaru, M. (2020). *Marketing Social Media Marketing Theory to Practitioners. International Review on Public And Non-Profit Marketing* 17(2). Retrieved via <https://doi:10.1007/s12208-020-00245-4> On July 21st, 2021.
- Maryland Sisters (n.d.). "Cross River State, Nigeria" Retrieved via <https://www.marylandsistersstates.org> On August 1st, 2021.
- McCombs M. & Shaw, D. (1968). "The agenda setting theory of the mass media" *Public opinion quarterly*, 36(3)106-187. Retrieved via <https://en.m.wikipedia.org> On April 13th, 2021
- Nardi, M. L. (2021). Ethics and Managerial Mindset in Politics. In *Computational Thinking for Problem Solving and Managerial Mindset Training* (pp. 252-265). IGI Global.
- Narwhal, A. (2021). "Social Marketing Theory". Retrieved via <https://narwhalstheorylog.wordpress.com/2016/12/04/social-marketing-theory/> On July 21st, 2021.

- Ngwoke, J. E. (2016). "Public perception of Billboard Advertising during the 2015 general election campaign period: A case study of Enugu North metropolis. Retrieved via <https://www.wikispe.org> On July 21st, 2021.
- Nyok, E. (2021). Personal communication [Personal interview].
- Oche, Ogaba (2010). "Presidential and gubernatorial elections in the fourth republic". Retrieved via <https://www.codesria.org> On Monday 8th March, 2021.
- Ojekwe, G. I. (2016). "Political adverts campaign and voting behaviour; Akinwumi Ambode's 2015 election campaign in Lagos State. <https://doi.org/10.20940/JAE/2016/vi5i2a1>
- Okay (n.d.). "Cross River State 2019 live elections results" Retrieved via <https://www.okay.com> On August 2nd, 2021
- Shiproh, V. (2007). "Rudiments of Commercialization. Boston: McGraw Hill.
- Siang, T. Y. (2020). "The Building Blocks of Visual Design" Retrieved via <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/article/the-building-blocks-of-visual-design> On July 21st, 2021.
- Tejumaiye, J; Simon, G; & Obia, V. (2018). Political Advertising in Nigeria's 2015 Presidential Election. *Global Media Journal* Vol. 16, No. 31:122.
- Wolf, Peter (2017). "Introducing Biometrics Technology in Elections". *International Institute for Democracy and Electoral Assistance*. Retrieved via <https://en.m.wikipedia.org> On 202103-012.
- Wroblewski, M. T. (2018). "The advantages and disadvantages of Billboards as an advertisement tool. Retrieved via <https://smallbusiness.chron.com> On March 8th, 2021.
- Yamane, Taro (1967). "Statistics: An introductory analysis, 2nd Ed., New York: Harper and Row.

APPENDIX A

Department of Mass Communication,
Faculty of Communication Technology,
Cross River University of Technology,
Calabar.
9th June, 2021

Dear Respondent,

I am a final year student of the department of Mass Communication, Cross River University of Technology (CRUTECH), Calabar. I am currently carrying out a research on the “The Influence of Billboard Advertising on Electorate's Voting Decision: A Study of the 2019 Cross River Gubernatorial Election”. Your response to this questionnaire will help me do analysis for academics.

I will ensure that every information and facts supplied by you shall be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be used solely for the purpose of this research work.

Your kind co-operation will be appreciated.

Yours Faithfully,

Essien, Essien Oku
(+234) 809 315 6830

**QUESTIONNAIRE ON THE INFLUENCE OF BILLBOARD
ADVERTISING ON ELECTORATES' VOTING DECISION/PATTERN: A
STUDY OF THE 2019 CROSS RIVER GUBERNATORIAL ELECTION**

SECTION A

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION (Please tick whichever is applicable)

1. Gender: Male Female
2. Marital Status: Single Married Separated
3. Religion: Christian Muslim
4. Academic Qualification: FSLC/WASSCE OND/B.SC MSC/PH.D
5. Occupation: Business Civil Servants Students
6. Age: 18 - 37years 38 - 57years 58years & above
7. Political party voted for during the 2019 CRS gubernatorial elections:
- PDP APC Others

SECTION B

PSYCHOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Please tick as: SA-strongly agree, A-agree, U-undecided, D-disagree, SD-strongly disagree

BILLBOARD AS A RELEVANT MEDIUM FOR POLITICAL ADVERTISING

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA	A	U	D	SD
8	Billboards were relevant means for the dissemination of political information during the 2019 gubernatorial election					
9	Billboards are more relevant than the other media of political advertising					
10	The Information on the billboards affected the attitudes of the electorates towards the electoral process					
11	Billboards Contributed to the electorates' choice of candidates					
12	Billboards were useful enough in the aspect of Electoral Orientation					

BILLBOARD AS A DIRECT APPEAL TO THE ELECTORATES

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA	A	U	D	SD
13	Political billboards were densely placed around the State during the 2019 gubernatorial election					
14	The Electorates actually believed in the billboard as a veritable medium for political advertising					
15	The ethnic background of a candidate actually contributed to the electorates' belief in the billboard messages					
16	Religious affiliations of the electorates equally affected the way they consumed the billboard messages					

17	The political party presented on a billboard contributed to the electorates' belief in the genuity of the messages					
INFLUENCE OF BILLBOARDS ON ELECTORATES						
S/N	STATEMENTS	SA	A	U	D	SD
18	The use of pictorial presentations on the billboards were sure enough to convince the electorates					
19	The visual elements employed in the design of the billboard layout equally contributed to the conviction of the electorates					
20	Billboards with fewer messages were more influential than the ones with more messages					

APPENDIX B

INTERVIEW INVENTORY

Interviewee 1	Mr. Efiok Ita Nyok
Date	16 th July, 2021
Time	20 Minutes
Location	Conflict management & Peace mediation Seminar Centre, Calabar
Questions	Responses Summary
Did your political party adopt the billboard as one of its campaign medium during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election?	In response to this question, Mr. Nyok stated that the Social Democratic Party (SDP) equally adopted the billboard as one of its campaign medium during the 2019 Cross River State gubernatorial election. In further responses, Mr. Nyok added that CRISAA (Cross River State Signage and Advertising Agency) had frustrated their usage of campaign billboards around the state owing to political sentiments and discrimination. In his word, “CRISAA under my friend as its General Manager, Stanley Nsemo, made sure that other parties outside the PDP could not really float their campaign materials particularly, the billboard. Our billboards were designed and produced but they were hardly mounted around the state”. Nevertheless, the interviewee admitted that the billboards were equally used as a campaign medium despite the challenges.
How relevant were the billboards to your political campaign strategies?	Responding to this, Mr. Nyok stated that the billboards were relevant to their campaign strategies through the messages which they communicated. He went on to analyse the advantage which the billboard has over the campaign handbills. In his word, “if you give people handbills, they can just keep them aside but billboards located at very strategic spots with high traffic maybe at junctions, roundabout or certain highways that are highly plied, people immediately see the message because the boards are massive, so they don’t need to strain to read what is there”. The interviewee pointed out that the contents of the message are immediately registered in the sub-consciousness of the people and this keeps the people thinking about it whenever it occurs in their minds.
Did your billboard usage during the political campaigns build up the confidence of victory at the polls?	Responding to this, Mr. Nyok admitted that the billboards did not build up their confidence of victory at their polls. In his statement “you do not depend on the communication strategy of the billboards alone to win election. It is one thing for the billboard to be located in strategic locations but other things applies which include vote buying, election rigging and the electoral processes as well. The billboard message is only there for the masses’ consumption but the decision of the voters and the entire stakeholders involved in the electoral process including INEC is a different ball game.” The interviewee pointed out that no matter how compelling the billboard messages may be, it is still left to the will of the voters (who consumed the message to either work with it or not) and other institutions involved in the process (to determine the winner).

<p>In what way would you measure that the electorates actually appreciated the contents of your billboard and were as well influenced by them?</p>	<p>In response to this, Mr. Nyok stated that the billboards are relevant means for public awareness and an individual uses this to declare his political Intentions/agitations to the general public. In his word, “sometimes when we go to the nooks and crannies of the state, people easily identify with us not because they have met us before but because our physical description matches some of the elements that are already reflected on the billboard.” The interviewee pointed out that the billboards go ahead of them to send the message even before their arrival, creates the desired awareness and even after their departure, the billboards still stand as a memorial to trigger the memories of previous encounters. Also, Mr. Nyok added that the billboard can still serve as a symbol that can provoke the people against them and to remind them or instigate their hatred or disagreement to the political party’s objectives.</p>
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Interviewee 2	Mr. Effanga Effiong
Date	20 th July, 2021
Time	15 Minutes
Location	Digital Graphics House, Calabar

Questions	Responses Summary
<p>With the ephemeral nature of the billboard, what will you suggest as the principles necessary to be adopted in the crafting of an appropriate billboard message?</p>	<p>Responding to this question, Mr. Effiong pointed out clearly that the nature of the billboard cannot be taken away from the billboard, putting it that it can never come to a point where Billboards will be squeezed into vehicles or stationed inside the house for continuous viewership and if this would ever happen at all, then such Technology has gone out of the periphery of the billboard and as such, should be given another identity. In his words, "to come to the point of establishing a convincing and convicting message, such message must be short, straight to the point and without any meandering. Such message must be witty and without unnecessary vocabularies, knowing too well that the audience members are a mixture of several blends". The Interviewee pointed clearly that crafting a message of long sentences with complex diction will not only mar the Communication objective but will defeat the initial essence and purpose of communication.</p>
<p>What visual principles will be appropriate for adoption during billboards design in order to capture and Influence the mobile audience (electorate)?</p>	<p>In response to this, Mr. Effiong said that there are numerous visual principles that must be adopted and accepted into a billboard layout, nevertheless this must be appropriately and carefully applied to avoid misconceptions and unintended negative impacts. In his statement "you must consider the colours you want to use for your billboard design and you must be able to interpret those colors to ascertain the fact that they can convey your message just the way you want them. Colours are vehicles as much as the words on the board, therefore if you use</p>

	<p>conflicting colours for your design, you tend to disseminate conflicting information. Meanwhile, visual principles includes, knowing the appropriate texture, shapes and sizes of elements. Whatever is mistakenly magnified which was meant to be on a low key standard will bring problem first to the message, secondly to your reputation as a designer and then to your client, whose objectives has been defeated by you". From the Interviewee's perspective, the careful selection and use of visual elements will enhance the message on the billboard.</p>
<p>What Billboard layouts/formats will you recommend for an effective political campaign?</p>	<p>Responding to this question, Mr. Effiong stated that there are various formats and sizes for billboard design, nevertheless as a graphic designer, one should be able to determine which layout and format will fit in well for an electoral situation. In his word, "sizes differs in billboard designing and such sizes are measured by inches. Well, to me, all sizes of Billboards can be used for political campaigns but you must consider that in an environment that is highly populated, larger Billboards will serve better than the small ones and for your Billboard to gain prominence especially during the campaign period, then a unique size with special design touches must be used on it to attract voters' attention".</p>

APPENDIX C
PHOTO CREDITS

Figure 1: Billboard campaign during the 2019 CRS gubernatorial elections Source:

Source: (<https://crossriverwatch.com>)

Figure 2: An electorate thumb-printing during the 2019 Cross River gubernatorial elections in the presence of electoral officials

Source: (<https://mobilewatch.com>)

APPENDIX D

TITLE GLOSSARY

S/N	WORDS	MEANING	Page No.
1.	Influence	This is the power or capacity of causing an effect on a targeted individual.	12
2.	Billboard	This is a structure composed of metal paper or a variety of other durable materials situated outdoors along the roads, in public places and on roof-tops of building for advertisement	10
3.	Advertising	This is to draw the public's attention and recognition to a personality, issue or situation by displaying the subject matter's image on a billboard for public viewership	10
4.	Electorate	This refers to the people who are eligible to vote in an election	11
5.	Voting	This refers to the act of expressing one's choice for a leader during the process of election	12
6.	Campaign	A series of operations undertaken to achieve a set goal.	11
7.	Decision	This refers to a situation of choice or judgment	12
8.	Gubernatorial	Pertaining to or relating to a governor	12

Note: The words defined above are the keywords that makes up the research topic. These keywords tends to appear in almost all pages of the contents, nevertheless, the page numbers displayed on the table above points significantly to the page of their initial appearance.